

Analysis the Satisfaction of the residents of Golbahar new town with the living conditions and its effects on Mashhad metropolis

Author's Details

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Abstract:

As the urban population increases in major cities of Iran, many of them face different issues. In Iran, new towns are built and located near cities to absorb their overflow population. Golbahar new town was built near Mashhad metropolis to reduce demographic, economic, social and physical problems of Mashhad, but in practice considering its goals, the town has not been able to reduce the problems of Mashhad metropolis. In this study, the relationship between the effects of living conditions on social, economic and physical aspects on the repopulation process in new towns has been investigated from the citizens' perspective. This study has been carried out in an empirical method and in some parts, descriptive-analytical methods have been applied; data collection was carried out using field methods (questionnaire) from a sample of 250 urban households. The study results show that there is a significant relationship between the living conditions and the repopulation process in the new towns from the citizens' perspective. They had a correlation coefficient of 0.570. Physical living conditions accounted for 35.7 percent of changes related to repopulation in new towns, and the living conditions in economic aspect only accounted for 20% of the dependent variable. Taking study results into account, the following guidelines were recommended for Golbahar new town: providing evenly distributed urban infrastructure and facilities, creating employment opportunities in various fields, making way for easy and good communications with metropolitan cities, building recreation and cultural centers and sport clubs for the youth and teenagers, providing and maintaining security as the basis of development in every place.

Key words: social security, employment opportunities, urban infrastructure and facilities, repopulation, reasons of residence.

Consequently, issues like unaffordable housing, unemployment, and illegal housing are reflected as the thorniest issues of urban life of our country whose alleviation needs comprehensive planning and attempts (Ziari, 2000).

Therefore, building new towns was put on the government's agenda as a strategic approach to these issues. New towns are among the national issues, and the national issues could not be solved with regional perspective, rather dealing with them demands national resolution and support (Qarakhlu, 2006). Now, after more than two decades from passing the Act No. 108 328 (dated 1986,3,4) by Council of Ministers about new towns, 14 towns have been under construction and repopulation phase and 11 new towns are in the preliminary stages, under investigation or implementation plan. There are different statements about the success or failure of this program. Those responsible for this project, namely the authorities in the ministry of roads and urban development and especially New Towns Development Company

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Statement of problem-Acute problems of urbanization led to new theoretical perspectives and solutions that have been reflected in national development policies. Building new towns has been proposed as one of the basic policies toward population growth and inflation in large cities. In different periods of history, new towns have been built around the world (Frank, 1972; 4). Building new towns in Iran goes back to past times; one can count many cities that were founded in a specified period (Piran, 1989; 126). In Iran, during the last three decades, the rapid growth of urban population has not been in proportion to the capacities of urban space facilities, and due infrastructure and required profession were not also provided. Since, spatial distribution of cities and population has not been based on a comprehensive plan which is in congruent with regional and provincial sectors, the issues resulted from the rapid urban population growth have become multifarious and convoluted.

new urban dynamic, balanced and self-sustaining town (Atash & Beheshtiha, 1998). Firman in his article "New town development in Jakarta metropolitan region: prospects for spatial differentiation" has come to the conclusion that for three reasons the new town development in Jakarta area reinforces the spatial differentiation. 1. It polarizes high and medium income groups, 2. High-income groups occupy very safe and suitable sites, 3. Instead of the municipality, developers manage the town (Firman, 2004).

Similar research on the function of new towns in Iran and absorbing the overflowing population of metropolitan cities have been conducted, but less has been done to investigate the role of living conditions in new towns' repopulation from the citizens' perspective. We will refer to some of them in the following line: Bezi and Afrasiyabi-Rad (2009) evaluated the function of Sadra new town in absorbing the overflow population of Shiraz metropolitan, and satisfaction of residents with this town and believed that many households living in the new town of Sadra were overflowing population of Shiraz that had migrated from Shiraz for the sake of low cost of land and housing. Nevertheless, the current residents' level of satisfaction was extremely low and 61.1 percent of them did not tend to have permanent residence in the new town. Qarakhlu and Panah-deh-khah (2009) evaluated the function of new towns around Tehran (Hashtgerd, Pardis, Parand and Andisheh) in absorbing the population of metropolises. Using "standardized score" on the predicted population for the specified time horizon, they believed that the four new towns around Tehran were not on the same level of success in absorbing the population. Zebar Dast and Jahanshahlu (2007) in evaluating the function of new town of Hashtgerd in absorbing the overflow population showed that although the new town has not fully achieved its expected programs, but the anticipated role and functions for the town in absorbing the overflow population of Karaj and Tehran metropolis have gradually been achieved. Ziari et al (2007) in a comparative analysis of the reasons for not achieving the goals of new towns in Iran using the ANP, and proposing an approach in Multiple Criteria Decision Making and also ranking the main causes of this effect, has examined the effectivity of these causes in all kinds of new towns and believe that among the new towns, continuous towns have suffered the greatest amount of loss from failing to achieve their goals; self-sustaining and satellite towns were respectively in the second

insist on the success of this policy, and are determined to continue and extend this policy, on the other hands, critics and experts in various fields, especially in urban development have had various ideas about the inefficiency and failure of this policy. In such circumstances, analyzing the function of these cities and the results of this policy seems essential.

Considering the difficulties and problems that mainly rise in continuous development of metropolitan cities that are due to high and increasing demands for housing, providing the land needed for development inside the cities has practically been a thorny problem and charges high costs. New towns as the detached extensions have largely tackled the problem, and have been able to provide appropriate conditions for mass housing, and with mass production of land and urban services, they have managed to relatively control land price, and naturally reduce the land price in metropolitan cities as demand goes up. Despite the relative success in controlling the growth and development of metropolitan cities, new towns failed to realize their goals, their major shortcoming was their inability to absorb population (Gholamiyan, 2010). In this study, having evaluated the living conditions of social, economic and physical aspects of new towns from the current residents' perspective, we tried to determine to what extent the living conditions of the new towns have influenced their repopulation. In other words, to what extent the living conditions provided in the new towns, have been effective in their relative success in achieving demographic goals?

1.2. Background of Research- In recent years, many efforts have been made by researchers and experts in various fields that are related to new town, some of them are discussed in the following lines: Extensive studies have been done at the international level about new towns, we mention a few of them; Ziari's study entitled "Planning and the function of new towns in Iran", has reviewed the new towns in Iran in two periods: before and after the Islamic Revolution, and he has also evaluated the process of new town planning and their function in Iran (Ziari, 2006). Atash and Beheshtiha in another study titled "new towns and their practical challenges: case study Foolad-Shahr", have examined the district of Isfahan and its new towns, Foolad-Shahr comprehensive plan, its development and its applicable challenges. They concluded that Foolad Shahr was far from being a

Kazemi-Sefat (2011) in evaluating the success of Hashtgerd new town in absorbing the overflow population of Tehran Metropolis believes that there is a big difference between the predicted population absorption and the number of residential units between 1996 and 2006 in Hashtgerd Comprehensive urban Plan and the status quo. Ebrahim et al. (2005) in an analysis of the necessity of building the new town of Golbahar and its role in decentralization of Mashhad Metropolis concluded that this town has failed to decentralize Mashhad Metropolis, to the extent that in terms of population, employment, housing and other predictions from 1996, even upto 2001, none of the above objectives were achieved. For example, until 2001 only about 10% (2397 people) of the predicted population for 1996 (24,000 people) have been achieved. Harirchi et al. (2009) in their study of citizens' quality of life in Pardis believed that increase in social capital improves the quality of life, and there is a significant correlation between satisfaction with neighborhood and quality of life, but there was not any significant correlation between the quality of life and the marital status and age groups.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMWORK

2.1. Theoretical Foundations: a new town is an independent community with a certain population, area, and distance from a metropolis, has predetermined planning, specific goals and also enjoys all necessary facilities required for an independent environment (Ziari, 2000). In various historical periods, there have been many towns around the world that were constructed with "different objectives" and one can call them "new towns". Greek philosophers have review the status of human life over the years and have suggested their ideal cities. Aristotle and Plato have spoken about optimal population size and the new towns' self-reliance. In the Renaissance, imaginative designs of new towns were considered as evidence of intelligence and human ability (Golany, 1979). After the Industrial Revolution, two theories of reformism and utopianism were advanced. Reformists believed that the spatial organization of towns should be within the technological framework and did not deny its totality, they also believed that the improvement and modernization of towns happens from inside. Utopianists believe in imaginary towns as opposed to industrial ones.

Thus, the plan of new towns has its roots in various theories, and Ebenezer Howard is its main theorist. Howard's theory was inspired by utopianist

and third ranking. Seyyed Fatemi and Hosseinzadeh Dalir (2010) in their analysis of the role of Sahand new town in spatial organization of Tabriz large urban space believed that despite the huge investments made in Sahand new town, it has had little effect in balancing the spatial organization of cities and their hierarchy in the province; furthermore, up to the end of the fourth development plan, it would have reached only 40 percent of its goals in repopulating new towns. Negahdari (2002) examining the function of Sadra new town, located in Shiraz urban area, believed that the town has not reached its original objectives or has faced delays, the underlying factors causing this process could be summarized as: finding proper land, land ownership, lack of basic services, rival settlements, lack of public participation and lack of appropriate job opportunities. Gholamiyan (2010) in his analysis of the role of new towns in absorbing the overflow population of metropolitan cities and decentralizing them believed that building new towns in Iran has failed to achieve its predetermined goals, besides they have not been successful enough in decentralization and absorbing the overflow population of metropolitan cities. Noriyan and Shayesteh-Paydar (2007) using AHP hierarchical analysis in evaluating the function of Golbahar new town have shown that the success of Golbahar new town compared to its optimal choices in its study was 23.79 percent, which signifies severe backwardness of the new town from its proposed programs.

Jahan-Shahlu (2007) in his analysis of the economic and demographic characteristics of the households living in the new town of Hashtgerd shows that although the town has quantitatively faced delays in achieving its demographic goals, partially qualitative correspondence of the results with the anticipated structure, much of the households belonging to middle and high income groups, relatively young structure of the town have all provided a good potential for improvement. Ebrahimzadeh et al. (2009) analyzing the role of Pardis new town in decentralization of Tehran metropolis, believed that this town has not been very successful in fulfilling his role i.e., absorbing certain parts of Tehran surplus population, and decentralization of the Tehran metropolis. Much of this failure was due to the lack of appropriate infrastructure and lack of employment opportunities in the town, which were caused by inefficient management and inappropriate urban planning that should be in accordance with development needs.

cities and, thus enhanced the fragile state of urban hierarchy and gave way to polarization.

Considering the status and role of new towns in urbanization process in Iran, four distinct periods could be studied: 1) The period between the two world wars or transition period: the new towns in Iran were developed without a clear strategy, and were mostly based on major functions or an originally rural core (Zahedan and Nowshahr) which are currently thriving, booming and are also considered as a town; 2) In the period between world war II and 1960s, new towns were developed based on an urban core without a certain strategy, they were based on dormitory or single function for development of oil industry and other branches of industry; 3) From 1960s until 1978 that could be called as take-off stage, the new towns were developed in line with the strategy of exploiting the natural resources; they lacked an original nucleus whose primary roles were regional development, providing housing and land; 4) After the Islamic revolution based on filtering strategy and spatial organizing of regional metropolises and Tehran megalopolis and distribution of balanced economic-social growth; 28 new satellite towns were planned in approved and non-approved forms without original core whose function were to create an optimal settlement and absorb the regional overflow population up to six million people in 2016 (Kazemi-Sefat, 2011).

2.3. The objectives of building new towns in Iran: the strategic planning of new towns in Iran initiated in 1970 and has continued up to now. The main objective of this strategy was to decentralize the population from large cities to some surrounding satellite towns. After the Islamic Revolution, from the beginning of 1985, the strategy of developing new towns was adopted in order to plan and control the rapid growth of population in large cities, and development of 12 new towns around large cities was approved. The major objectives of building new towns could be divided into two major categories:

A) the objectives of building new towns with regard to metropolitan cities: 1) to absorb the overflow population of the metropolises, 2) to prevent uncontrolled growth and shape of the metropolises, 3) to provide suitable conditions for discontinuous development of the metropolises, 4) to prevent the uncontrolled destruction of agricultural lands, gardens and pleasant urban views around the metropolises 5) to reduce congestion,

thoughts. Howard believed that the theory of "garden city" is a way for dealing with population growth in large cities, organization and spatial distribution of population and industry. He claimed that the goals of building garden cities are to create a functional structure, optimize population size and area, employment and self-reliance, development of green belts, optimum density and public ownership of land. He implemented two plans of garden cities (1928) before his death (Hall, 1992). As a result of revolutionary dreams of utopianists and reformist ideas of Howard and their compliance with national planning policies in the UK and other countries, the notion of new town was accepted as a liberal opportunity for reform and providing a better way for urban life.

2.2. The process of developing new towns in Iran: In the past three decades, rapid growth of urbanization in Iran has not been in accordance with the potentials for equipping the urban spaces and providing the infrastructure needed to create productive jobs. Since the distribution and control of urban spaces have not been carried out in the framework of a comprehensive program which was based on regional coordination, the problems resulting from rapid growth of urban population has got complex dimensions, resulting in issues such as expensive housing, unemployment and other informal settlements, and to the most severe form has appeared in the urban appearance of the country whose remedy requires comprehensive effort and planning.

Iran, after a transitional period in a take-off stage (1961-1978) joined global capitalism and for this purpose the necessary infrastructure for the full deployment of capitalism were developed so that Iran's economy may reach its accomplishment. In the take-off stage, in addition to the existing functions of cities, the industrial function of the cities was especially expanded (Athari, 1989). Growing urbanization in Iran in the take-off stage due to high correlation between the center-periphery and suburban development resulted from petrodollars and alternative import strategies, pave the way for strengthening single megalopolitan system in Tehran and regional metropolitan cities. Therefore, the facilities and populations of suburban cities were depleted that led to intense concentration of population and capital in Tehran metropolis and regional metropolises (Mashhad, Isfahan, Shiraz and Tabriz) developed independent of the development of their upper city, namely Tehran, and the lower

clear function and specific role in the urban system, up to now have not been very successful, even if they manage to absorb future population, they would turn to residential neighborhoods, institutional dormitories, and urban ghettos which are void of any liveliness and identity.

4) Inappropriate location for new cities: in three thousand years of urbanization in Iran, natural and climatic factors have played an important role in population settlement. These factors were quite effective not only in variety and distribution of biological centers but also in socio-economic circumstances of the population (Shia, 2001, 11), to the extent that 1161 urban areas and 60 thousands rural areas have almost totally been affected by this rule, thus one may conclude that people always choose the locations that best meet their optimum criteria in consistent with the natural environment and living conditions.

5) Lack of efficient transportation system between the new town and metropolitan cities: the relatively long distance between the new town and metropolitan cities with an average distance of 35 km (Department of Housing and Urban Development, 2007; 29) and lack of public transportation facilities such as subway, highways have paved the way for isolation of new towns in country's urban system (Negahban-Marvi, 2002), for example, one of the reasons behind the success of five new town built around Seoul is their access to downtown through subway system (Ma'sum, 2001).

6) Lack of accurate prediction: After the Islamic revolution, one of the reasons for building new towns was the anticipation of a population amounting to 130 million and a urban population of 96 million which were all based on 1986 statistics, in which household's total fertility rate was 6.5 % and population growth rate was 3.7 %. But during the following periods demographic indices such as fertility rate, etc. drastically reduced. (Ziari, 2006)

pollution and traffic of the metropolises and provide attractive and quality life in new towns.

B) general and peripheral objectives of building and expanding new towns: 1) to create employment opportunities, 2) to provide suitable and affordable land and housing for low-and middle-income people, 3) to facilitate regional balance and develop trans-regional service centers, 4) to prevent uncontrolled urban development, 5) to prevent irregular rises in land price and provide suitable land for construction in urban area (Monavari and Tabibiyan, 2006)

2.4. The reasons behind the new towns' failure in Iran: problems and reasons that caused the failure of the new towns could be summarized as:

1) Mere imitating of foreign models and using none-native ideas for building these new towns: one of major causes of new towns' failure in Iran was adopting mere imitation of foreign models and not using native ideas for building these new towns, to the extent that all the models provided by the consultant groups for construction of new towns have been imitations of Western models and plans with modernist design method of 1930s (case study, the artificial lake built in Golbahar new town) (Daneshpour, 2006).

2) The willingness of low-income people to reside in new towns: Peter Hall believed that one of the limitations of new towns in London suburb was attracting skilled and semi-skilled sectors of the community and their failure to attract low income and impoverished classes of central London (Zekavat, 1993), on the contrary, in Iran the process of repopulation in new towns is quite reverse, new towns have largely turned to a place for the lowest classes of people who are not rich enough to afford housing and living costs in metropolitan cities (case study, Golbahar new town).

3) Lack of a clear position in the hierarchy of urban networks: the new towns due to lack of a

Figure 1: conceptual model of the study (Research findings, 2012)

hundred and ten thousand people. The second zone included ten neighborhoods and two regional centers and major downtown was designed in line with the first zone downtown extension, and this zone was also planned to accommodate one hundred and fifteen thousand people. Cultural, religious, sport, and recreational applications and the like were also predicted based on the comprehensive plan (Mehrazan Consultant Engineers, 1998).

In 2011, this town had a population of nearly 13371. In terms of political divisions, center of Golbahar district is located in Chenaran County, and in terms of urban management, it is administered by Golbahar New Town Development Company (Golbahar Bakhshdari, 2011). Studies of Golbahar

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Score of the study area:- Golbahar new town with latitude of 37, 36 and longitude of 59, 14 and the average height of 1250 m above sea level, is located in the plain between the mountains of Hezar Masjid and Binalood, 45 km northwest of Mashhad at Mashhad-Quchan road. Golbahar urban area is 4,000 hectares and its design follows a linear-checked organization. The planned area includes two urban zones and four regions. The first zone includes some parts of the downtown, construction of eleven neighborhoods and two region centers were anticipated, and the central core of Golbahar new town was formed in this zone, and the resettlement program have been made for one

project is being carried out in 1,000 acres of land in the town. According to the conducted researches, the physical progress of the project in 2011 were about 45%, for example in neighborhood 1 to 6, center of the first region, construction area included Golbahar recreational complex, and parts of neighborhood 7 and 22 (area for light industries) (research findings, 2011).

new town, as the first satellite town of Mashhad were initiated in 1987, in 1992 the construction process began and from 1995 the repopulation and accommodation began (Noriyan and Shayeste-Paydar 2007). In September 2011, the first phase of the town based on comprehensive and detailed plan of the town was almost executed and different neighborhoods such as Farhangiyan, Pardis and Parand were built. Furthermore, Mehr housing

Figure 2.0 location of the study area (Governor of Khorasan Razavi, 2012)

independent variables and the process of residence in Golbahar new town was considered as the dependent variable. Initial research question is that considering the activities of New Towns Development Company in a two-decade long period in providing infrastructural facilities and services in Golbahar new town, how do such activities make way for absorption and retention of overflow population of Mashhad metropolis to this town? Therefore, the present study sought to find the answer to the above question. This study's hypothesis could be formulated in this form: "From citizens' perspective, to what extent the living conditions in Golbahar new town have been effective in absorbing overflow population of Mashhad metropolis."

3.3. Index and variables- better understanding and more precise geographic characteristics of the situation in different fields and different levels of

3.2. Research Method- This study has been carried out using empirical method and in some parts descriptive-analytical methods have been applied; data collection was carried out using field methods (questionnaires and interviews) and other required data such as analytical-conceptual framework of the research, documents and censuses have been obtained through the library search. In Golbahar new town, a population of over 13/4 thousand people live in 3940 households, using Cochran sampling formula, a sample size of 250 households were selected from the residential units, and urban households questionnaires were filled out and the required data were obtained. Having collected and processed the data by SPSS, Data were analyzed and the subject was investigated.

In this study, living conditions regarding the social, economic and physical aspects were taken as

variables were introduced. Variables were assessed by 12 indices and 38 items. All items were set up based on Likert spectrum (very low, low, medium, high, very high) and their validity and reliability were confirmed based on Cronbach's alpha with a reliability level between 0.65 to 0.77.

access lead to perfect and processed information of the desired location. To achieve this goal, a series of indices are used, they can show a level of growth and development of geographic locations based on selected criteria (Kalantari, 2003: 112). To investigate the effectively of living conditions in Golbahar new town on repopulation process, four

Table 1: Variables and parameters of the study and measured indexes

Variable	Indix	Item number	Variable reliability (Cronbach Alpha)
Social conditions of life	Social Security	3	0.65
	Satisfaction with location	4	
	Willingness to reside	2	
Economic conditions of life	Employment opportunities	3	0.67
	High income groups	2	
	Economic dependence on the metropolitan city	2	
Physical conditions of life	Efficient transportation system	3	0.77
	urban facilities	5	
	selection for appropriate location for new town	2	
residential status	Previous residential place	2	0.75
	Duration of residence	1	
	Reason of residence	9	

Reference: Research findings, 2012.

of 2006-11, it is anticipated that the population of Golbahar new town in 2016 would be about 31409.

However, based on the minimum repopulation scenario and the statistics of health center in 2011, only 11.6 % of the anticipated population for Golbahar new town has been fulfilled, and it is predicted that in 2016 only 16.5% of minimum repopulation scenario would be fulfilled. As one would expect, in the last two years some measures have been taken in carrying out Mehr housing project, and it is promised that they would construct residential units for at least 30 thousand households, it is predicted that repopulation trend would change in 2011-2016, but the likelihood of achieving the minimum scenario in development plan seems unlikely.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. The process of repopulation in Golbahar new town: in demographic changes of Golbahar new town we see that according to the Statistical Center of Iran, total population of the town from 179 people in 1996 has reached to 3198 in 2001 and 7039 in 2006, the annual population growth rate equivalent for 2001-6 has been 17.1%. According to this growth rate, it is anticipated that in 2011 its population would be 15 493, and in 2016 its population would be 34 101. According to statistics of Chenaran health center, the population of Golbahar new town in 2001 was 5692, and in 2006 its population has reached 13371. The annual population growth rate in the 2000s was equal to 25.2% and the annual population growth rate for 2006-11 would be 18.6 %; According to growth rate

Table 2: repopulation rate in Golbahar new town

Population \ Year		1996	2001	2006	2011	2016
Statistical Center of Iran		179	3198	7039	15493★	34101★
Health Center		-	1410	5692	13 371	31409★★
Minimum Scenario		240 00	41 000	70 000	115 300	190 000
optimum scenario		45 000	77 900	135 000	222 000	365 000
Percentage of repopulation	SCI	0.7	7.8	10	13.4	17.9
	Health Center	-	3.4	8.1	11.6	16.5

Reference: Statistical Center of Iran (SCI), 2006 and 1996 Chenaran Health Center, 2011

★ Predicted based on average annual growth rate of 2001-6 half-decade.

★★ Predicted based on average annual growth rate of 2006-11 half-decade.

Overall, social conditions of life in the new town from citizens' perspective with the standard deviation of 0.65 were 3.016. Among the three indices of the mentioned variable, citizens' willingness to reside in the town with a mean of 1.3 and standard deviation of 0.79 had the highest ranking, and access to social security for citizens, with a mean of 2.96 and standard deviation of 1.1 had the lowest rank.

4.2. Evaluation of the social conditions of life in Golbahar new town from citizens' perspective: In order to evaluate the function of social conditions of life in Golbahar new town, indices of social security, satisfaction with work place and willingness to reside are used. Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used for confirmation of normal data, and it was proven with 0.081. Therefore the results obtained by this variable will be approved.

Table 3: evaluation of social conditions of life in Golbahar new town from citizens' perspective

Index	Items	Very low	Low	medium	High	Very much	Mean	K2 Pierson test
Social Security	Satisfaction with provided comfort and security in Golbahar	11.2	12.2	41.3	17.3	17.9	3.18	0.000
	Willingness to walk in urban streets at night	28.1	22.9	15.6	14.6	18.8	2.73	0.018
Satisfaction with residence area	Satisfaction with residence in Golbahar	13	12.4	40.4	14.5	19.7	3.16	0.000
	Satisfaction with life along with people of different ethnic and cultural background in Golbahar	21	19	37.9	10.3	11.8	2.73	0.000
	Satisfaction with citizens' participation in urban affairs	34.2	18.1	27.5	13	7.3	2.41	0.000
	participation of citizens in promoting urban affairs	13.6	6.3	13.6	26.7	39.8	3.73	0.000
Willingness to reside	The probability to leave Golbahar new town	23.4	16.7	14.6	13	32.3	3.14	0.000
	attachment to Golbahar new town	15	16.1	32.6	21.8	14.5	3.05	0.000

Reference: Research findings, 2012.

order to assess the economic conditions of life in Golbahar new town the following indices were used: employment opportunities, residence of high income people and economic dependence on metropolitan cities. Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used for confirmation of normal data which were proved by 0.378; therefore the data from this variable will be approved. Overall, average economic conditions of life in Golbahar new town from citizen's perspective with standard deviation of 0.85 was 2.95. Among the three indices of the mentioned variable, from citizen's perspective, residence of high income classes with an average of

In addition to the above questions, citizens were enquired that what were Golbahar's most important social issues? 22.2% of citizens have mentioned addiction as the most important social issue, 18.1% various harassments, 14.6 % lack of social security, 8.3 % strafes and conflicts, 7.6% robberies and 29.2% had chosen other options. Therefore, the responses to the above questions nearly agree with two previous questions relating to social security in Golbahar new town.

4.3. Assessment of economic conditions in Golbahar new town from citizens' perspective: In

citizens with an average of 2.66 and standard deviation of 0.99 had the lowest rank.

3.3 and standard deviation of 1.009 had the highest rank, and access to employment opportunities for

Table : assessment of economic conditions of life in Golbahar new town from citizens' perspective

Index	Item	Very low	Low	medium	High	Very much	Mean	K2 Pierson test
Employment opportunities	Satisfaction with employment opportunities created in Golbahar	39.9	19.7	25.5	5.9	9	2.24	0.000
	Tendency to invest in employment opportunities	16.1	23.1	25.3	15.1	20.4	3.01	0.127
	Satisfaction with investment in process in creating employment opportunities in Golbahar new town	21.3	24.7	29.2	13.5	11.2	2.69	0.000
Residence of high income classes	conditions provided for residence of high income classes	18.3	16.7	17.7	23.7	23.7	3.18	0.371
	presence of low income classes as Mehr housing project in Golbahar began	13.8	12.8	17	28.7	27.7	3.44	0.000
Attachment to a metropolitan city	Willingness to investor in Golbahar new town	20.6	14.8	21.2	18	25.4	3.13	0.211

Reference: Research findings, 2012.

4.4. Assessment of physical living conditions in Golbahar new town from citizens' perspective: In order to evaluate the physical conditions of life in Golbahar new town the following indices were used: efficient transportation systems, urban facilities and equipment, location of the new town. Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to confirm the normality of the data and their normality were proven by 0.147; therefore the data from this variable will be approved. Overall, the average physical conditions of life in the new town from citizens' perspective with standard deviation of 0.80 were 2.65. From three indices of the mentioned variables, access to urban facilities and equipment with an average of 2.73 and standard deviation of 0/94 had the highest rank and access to efficient transportation system for citizens with an average of

In addition to the above questions, citizens were asked where their current place of work was. 74.3 percent of residents worked in Golbahar new town, 19 percent worked in Mashhad, 2.8 percent worked in Chenaran, and 3.9 percent worked in the surrounding villages or other locations. Thus the combining the results of this question and items related to the economic dependence on the metropolis, it could be concluded that the current citizens of Golbahar new town are economically least dependent on the metropolis. It should be noted that the items designed for the town's economic dependence should be viewed reversely. To confirm this, we asked the citizens how long it takes to get to their place of work. 77.2% percent stated that it took them less than 30 minutes and this confirms that their place of work were located in Golbahar new town or the surrounding areas.

have mentioned other reasons. Thus, combining the results of these questions and items related to efficient transportation system, it could be concluded that the current citizens of Golbahar new town have many transportation issues, particularly in commuting to the metropolis. Due to the lack of commercial services in Golbahar new town and the fact that 66.8 percent of citizens buy their commercial goods from Mashhad metropolis, transportation issues are more pressing.

2.5 and standard deviation of 1.01 had the lowest rank.

In addition to the above questions, the citizens were asked what the most important transportation issues of Golbahar were. In response to this question, 73.3 percent of citizens believed that shortage of public transportation vehicles in Golbahar new town were the most important transportation issues, 15.8 percent have mentioned high fares and transportation costs, 7.8 percent lack of security and safety in sidewalks and 3 percent

Table 5: assessment of the physical conditions of life in Golbahar new town from citizens' perspective

Index	Items	Very low	Low	medium	High	Very much	Mean	K2 Pierson test
Efficient transportation system	Satisfaction with the intercity transportation system	20.5	10	35.8	20	13.7	2.96	0.000
	Satisfaction with Golbahar intracity transportation system	46.8	18.1	23.4	6.9	4.8	2.05	0.000
urban facilities and equipment	Satisfaction with existing health facilities	43.1	20.2	22.9	8	5.9	2.13	0.000
	Satisfaction with existing educational and cultural facilities	25.9	18.5	31.2	10.6	13.8	2.68	0.000
	Satisfaction with the urban services such as (garbage collecting, ...) By Development Company of the new town	12.2	10.1	28.3	22.3	27.1	3.42	0.000
	Satisfaction with the distance between residential area and downtown	28.9	15.3	28.9	11.1	15.8	2.69	0.000
Location of the new town	Suitability of the location of Golbahar new town	14.1	9.2	33.5	19.5	23.8	3.3	0.000
	Satisfaction with leisure facilities in the town	49.5	16.5	25	3.2	5.9	1.99	0.000

Reference: Research findings, 2012.

used: reasons of residence, previous residential place and the duration of residence in the new town. Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used for confirmation of normal data, and their normality

Assessment of residential status (repopulation) in Golbahar new town from citizens' perspective: to examine the residential status (repopulation) in Golbahar new town the following indices were

town from citizens' perspective with standard deviation of 2.97 was 0.80.

was proven with the value of 0.662, so the data from this variable will be approved. Overall, the average of data related to the reasons of residence in the new

Table 6: Assessment of residential status (repopulation) in Golbahar new town from citizens' perspective

Index	Items	Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very much	Mean	K2 Pierson test
Reasons for residence in Golbahar new town	Social peace	11.4	5.4	22.7	22.7	37.8	3.7	0.000
	suitable climatic conditions	7	2.7	10.2	26.7	53.5	4.17	0.000
	Belief in a better future	15	6.4	22.5	23.5	32.6	3.52	0.000
	suitable municipal services	29.6	19.9	25.8	12.4	12.4	2.58	0.000
	planned urbanization	28.6	18.4	18.9	18.4	15.7	2.74	0.055
	Proper facilities provided by institutions	39.6	15.9	25.8	9.9	8.8	2.32	0.000
	affordable land	33.5	15.1	24.3	9.7	17.3	2.62	0.000
	Proximity to work place	31.7	9.4	17.2	15.6	26.1	2.95	0.000
	Residence of other relatives	54.1	17.5	12	7.7	8.7	1.99	0.000

Reference: Research findings, 2012.

10 years. So, more than half of the current citizens of Golbahar new town have been residing less than 5 years in this town.

4.5. The correlation between living conditions and repopulation of Golbahar new town: In this study, considering the data type (ordinal or relative), Pearson method was used to calculate their correlation coefficient. "Correlation" shows the value of correlation coefficient, if the value of probability test is less than 0.5, it indicates that there is a correlation between variables. Data frequency in this study was 250, which is the number of families residing in Golbahar town. According to the results of the Pearson correlation coefficient test, significant is 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis test based on the lack of significant correlation between the three variables of the research and residential status is rejected. Thus, there is a significant relationship between social, economic and physical conditions of life in Golbahar new town and residential status (repopulation Mashhad metropolitan city).

The current households were enquired about their previous place of residence and their responses revealed that 64.9 % lived in Mashhad, 15.1 % in surrounding villages, 6.5% percent in Chenaran town and 1.5 percent in other locations. Thus, putting the results of this question together, it could be concluded that the current citizens of Golbahar new town have migrated from a metropolis. Furthermore, the citizens were questioned about the ownership of their previous residence. The responses revealed that 48/4 percent of their previous houses belonged to them, 43.3 percent was rented, 2.7 percent was institutional, 4.9 percent was with no rent and 0.5 percent has mentioned other forms of ownership. It can be concluded that the majority of current residents are previous residents of Mashhad metropolis; nearly half of them did not own a house in the metropolis. The citizens were enquired about the duration of their residence in Golbahar new town, the responses showed that 15.1 % have lived less than a year, 40% between one to 5 years, 21.6% between 5 to 10 years and 23.2 % over

Table 7: the relationship between variables related to living conditions in Golbahar new town and residential status (repopulation) from citizens' perspective

Variables	Pearson correlation coefficient	significant	Test value
social status	0.441	0.000	null hypothesis rejected
economic situation	0.442	0.000	null hypothesis rejected
physical condition	0.530	0.000	null hypothesis rejected
living conditions	0.570	0.000	null hypothesis rejected

Reference: Research findings, 2012

variation. In the ANOVA table, the sum of squares, degrees of freedom, mean square, Fisher's statistic, and the significant level of regression are reported. Significance level or P-Value is 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05. Therefore, null hypothesis, based on insignificance of regression model, is rejected with 99% confidence interval. Thus, regression model is statistically significant.

4.6. The effect of living conditions in Golbahar new town on repopulation process: To investigate the effects of living conditions in the new towns on the process repopulation from the citizens' perspective, stepwise regression model was used. The coefficient of 0.34 shows that the linear regression of independent variables on the dependent variable explains about 34% of the total

Table 7: The effect of living conditions in Golbahar new town on repopulation process

The independent variables	Parameter Estimation		Standard coefficient (Beta)	T-statistics	Significant level	Result
	Value	Standard deviation				
★ constant	0.953	0.238	-	4.010	0.000	It is significant in the model
Social	0.167	0.095	0.137	1.749	0.082	It is not significant in the model
Economic	0.188	0.069	0.200	2.711	0.000	It is significant in the model
physical	0.360	0.077	0.357	4.703	0.000	It is significant in the model

★ Dependent variable: residential status (repopulation)

Reference: Research findings, 2012

metropolis. According to the results of Pearson correlation coefficient, the value of probability test is 0/000 which is smaller than 0/05. Therefore, being based on the lack of significant correlation between variables, the null hypothesis of the test was rejected. The living conditions in Golbahar new town with the correlation coefficient of 0/570 have been effective in the process of repopulation. From the three aspects of living condition, the physical conditions with 36 percent have had the greatest effect. It could be concluded that by providing the appropriate physical conditions for citizens, repopulation of Golbahar new town would not be unexpected.

Providing the following conditions for citizens, the urban managers of Golbahar new town may hope for absorbing the overflow population of Mashhad metropolis:

1. To provide urban infrastructure and equipment (telephone, gas, public parking, parks, green spaces, etc.) in an equitable distribution in Golbahar new town to reduce citizens' problems, improve their status and increase their willingness to remain in the town;
2. To create employment opportunities in different sectors especially commercial sector, to build small industrial areas near the new town to remove its role as a dormitory and turn it to an independent and self-sustaining town;
3. With regard to the ownership of lots of lands, it is proposed to construct centers that are not available in Mashhad, for example places for motorcycle and car races, etc.;
4. To provide suitable public transportation and communication infrastructure for fast, comfortable and safe travelling to Mashhad metropolis for instance through development of railroad;
5. To provide various services in Golbahar new town so that people may not have to commute to Mashhad metropolis, and reduce pendulum migration of residents to downtown;
6. Efficient management of land and housing markets;
7. To implement the principles of modern urban planning and urban design in beautification of the urban appearance with the participation of citizens;

In Table 7 for each of the regression parameters, estimated values of parameters, standard deviation of the estimated parameters, the estimated standardized regression parameters, the test statistic and significant level of parameters' estimation have been reported. According to the obtained results, only for the variable of social conditions of life in the new town P-Value is more than 0.05, in other words the effect of changing social conditions is not significant in the model. Thus, regression model is as follows:

$$\text{Repopulation (residence)} = 0.953 + (\text{Physical conditions} \times 0.36) + (\text{economic conditions} \times 0.188)$$

5. CONCLUSION AND REMARKS

Studies on the success of new towns in Iran are indicative of their relative success in various situations. However, Golbahar as a new dormitory town around Mashhad, slowly developing by sales and pre-sales of its apartments, only with government assistance has managed to keep up, and this incurs irreversible damage to the economy of the region. It is clear that regarding the current population of the town and the future population predicted for this town, it has failed to fulfill its functions and roles. Practically, this town has failed to reduce the problems of Mashhad metropolis, and only a small population lives in this town, to the extent that from day to day, economic, social, physical and demographic issues of Mashhad increase and no reduction is observed in migration to Mashhad. The reasons for failure of this town partly lies in the metropolis itself (lack of control on suburban areas, and their unplanned linear development, like Elahieh lands) and partly lie inside the new town (inefficient fulfillment of living conditions in social, economic and physical aspects).

This study has dealt with the second aspect of the subject, namely the inefficient fulfillment of living conditions in Golbahar new town (the reasons for failure of such towns in absorbing the overflow population of metropolises), it was determined that living conditions in the social, economic and physical aspects for citizens were in a satisfactory level, and taking the research hypothesis into account, it becomes clear that from the citizens' perspective to what extent the living conditions in Golbahar new town have been effective in absorbing the overflow population of Mashhad

organs to support private sector and local investors to construct industrial and manufacturing units for entrepreneurs so that they can attract young jobseekers and fulfill the role of the new town;

12. To provide and maintain security as the infrastructure of development in any location, especially in Golbahar new town seems necessary;
 13. To construct hospitals, pharmacies, culture centers and provide cultural services, to build some centers for promotion of ideas and communications. Providing services by the public sector in the town increases life satisfaction and consequently improves the quality of life.
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8. To build a cemetery to give Golbahar new town an identity;
 9. To build educational and cultural centers for women, since the head of most households are working in Mashhad and just spend the night in the new town.
 10. To build recreation, cultural and sport centers for young people, if there are not enough leisure facilities, sport and education centers for the youth, they would have no interest in living in the new town, and would prefer to live in their metropolitans despite all its other issues and assume a position for themselves;
 11. Better utilization of capital and facilities together with the cooperation of related state

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